

Supplementary material 1: Table S1. The geographic coordinates of known localities of the model species

N	E	Comment	Source
<i>Aeropedellus baliolus</i>			
52.89	70.63		Kadyrbekov et al., 2017
52.82	70.8		Kadyrbekov et al., 2017
48.64	72.64		Kadyrbekov et al., 2017
49.68	72.69	type locality	Bey-Bienko and Mistshenko, 1951
51.8	72.88		unpublished data, 1980
49.58	72.9		Bey-Bienko and Mistshenko, 1951
52.51	73.31		unpublished data, 1980
50.1	73.39		unpublished data, 1980
50.72	73.61		unpublished data, 1980
53.38	75.39		Childebaev, 2002
53.28	75.54		unpublished data, 1980
53.22	75.73		unpublished data, 1980
52.17	77.05		unpublished data, 1980
53.7	77.83		unpublished data, 1985
53.7	77.85		unpublished data, 1985
53.68	77.87		unpublished data, 1985
53.73	77.88		unpublished data, 1985
53.15	78.2		unpublished data, 2005
53.67	78.25		Sergeev, 2021b
53.35	78.28		unpublished data, 1980
52.85	78.57		Sergeev, 2021b
52.98	78.68		Bey-Bienko and Mistshenko, 1951
53.1	78.73		unpublished data, 2006
52.63	82.13		unpublished data, 1992, 2000
<i>Asiotmethis jubatus</i>			
<i>known localities</i>			
52,12	79,32	type locality	Uvarov, 1926
51,38	79,8		Berezhkov, 1956
50,45	80,23		Berezhkov, 1956
50,82	80,3		Berezhkov, 1956
51,52	80,35		Tarbinskij, 1925
50,78	80,4		Berezhkov, 1956
47,97	80,4		Zoological Institute
51,05	81,03		Bey-Bienko, 1930b
51,16	81,3		Berezhkov, 1956
53,08	81,4		Berezhkov, 1956
49,69	81,52		Bey-Bienko, 1930a
48,38	84,46		unpublished data, 1976
48,38	84,52		unpublished data, 1976
47,8	88,09		Bey-Bienko and Mistshenko, 1951
validation point			
51,37	80,11		unpublished data, 2024

Mesasippus arenosus

known localities

51	81	type locality of <i>Mesasippus arenosus arenosus</i>	Bey-Bienko, 1930a
51,05	81,03		Berezhkov, 1956
50,75	80,28		Berezhkov, 1956
52,12	79,32		unpublished data, 2006
51,83	79,83		unpublished data, 2004, 2006
51,88	77,38		unpublished data, 1972
50,9	78,47		unpublished data, 1972

pseudo-occurrences

51,93	79,39		
51,74	79,43		
51,62	79,45		
51,24	79,97		
52,19	78,57		
52,58	79,21		
50,87	79,55		
48,33	83,34	possible type locality of <i>Mesasippus arenosus zaisanicus</i>	

validation point

51,3	80,38		unpublished data, 2024
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